

THEORY AND METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING MUSIC IN SCHOOL PRACTICE

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Abstract. *Today, in all areas of “art pedagogy” at all its levels, there is a search for more advanced forms and methods of teaching that meet the demands of the times and are capable of solving the problems that the country faces on the threshold of the third millennium.*

Keywords: *formation, attributive qualities, properties of a music teacher, process, professional training, theoretical and scientific-practical analysis, pedagogical foundations, music teacher.*

The specific branch of education that is connected with teaching musical disciplines is no exception. Here, too, intensive research is underway into more effective methods and ways of educational work with students, and attempts are being made to introduce theoretical and practical innovations into the work of music teachers. In the last two or three decades, the scientific and practical efforts of leading domestic specialists have been marked by significant achievements. They have developed problems of organizing the teaching of music, the content, forms and methods of educational work; problems of expanding and enriching the spiritual and general cultural knowledge of student musicians; problems of a psychological and pedagogical nature, etc.

Love for music, the need for it are formed in a child primarily in the process of listening to it, thanks to which musical perception develops in children, the foundations of musical culture are laid. The term "musical perception" in music pedagogy has two meanings. In the first, more capacious, musical perception is understood as the mastering by children of various types of musical activity in classes (singing, playing children's musical instruments, musical and rhythmic movements) [2].

Another meaning of the term, narrower, implies listening to music directly: getting to know musical works of various genres and styles, composers, performers. In our lives, music sounds everywhere - on the radio, television, in records, theaters and cinemas. But such encounters of children with music are random, and for the development of musical sensitivity, consistent guidance of the listening process is necessary. In order to develop an aesthetic perception of music, it is important not only to experience and understand its content, but also to distinguish between individual means of musical expression. D. B. Kovalevsky drew the attention of teachers to the fact that music will only fulfill its aesthetic, cognitive and educational role when children truly learn to listen to it and think about it[5].

The program for listening to music in kindergarten is determined mainly by educational tasks, not by training tasks, since the information received by children while listening to music is still very limited. The main goal of this type of activity is to introduce children to music, to cultivate a stable interest and love for it. In accordance with this goal, the main educational task in listening to music is the formation of the initial foundations of musical culture: - familiarizing children with modern, classical works accessible to their perception, as well as with folk musical creativity, differentiating them by genres, types; - developing musical sensitivity in children, the ability to respond emotionally to music, empathize with the feelings expressed in it; - development

of the ability to remember musical works, their content, character, means of musical expression; gradual formation of ideas about music; - education of an evaluative attitude towards music and its performance, which is the initial manifestation of musical taste; - formation of the skill of listening to music; - creation of a fund of favorite children's works[3].

Forms of listening to music Listening to music in kindergarten is carried out in various forms. 1. Children encounter listening to music in the process of all musical work with them - in singing, musical-rhythmic movements, musical-didactic games, playing instruments. Before starting to learn dances or games, children are offered to listen to the corresponding musical material. That is, listening to music is a methodical technique for working on teaching all types of musical activity. 2. Part of the music lesson is devoted to special listening to music, not related to singing and movement. Children listen to small fragments of musical works or short musical works in their entirety, both vocal and instrumental, analyze them, get acquainted with musical terminology, genres and their varieties, learn the names of composers. 3. With children of the senior and preparatory groups, when they have already acquired the skills of listening to music, can distinguish its character, means of expression and are able to concentrate their attention on the musical sound for a longer period of time, listening to music can be carried out as an independent activity.

This activity is sometimes carried out in the second half of the day, as it is a calm type of activity that does not require much activity from the children. The lesson usually includes 4-5 pieces, of which 1-2 are instrumental, and the rest are vocal. A conversation is held with the children about what they heard - the simplest analysis of a piece of music. In addition to music, it is good to include in such a lesson a short story, a fairy tale, a poem that corresponds to musical images.

A positive aspect is the unification of the lesson around one topic. For example: "Songs and Dances of Our People," "Winter," "It's Nice in Our Garden," etc. Each lesson on listening to music includes new (no more than one or two pieces) and material that is already familiar to the children. The new material is subsequently consolidated during regular music lessons. 4. Children encounter listening to music at leisure evenings and holidays. Concerts are organized that are entirely dedicated to listening to music. Unlike lessons on listening to music, there is no analysis of musical works. The titles of the pieces are given or a short introductory speech by an adult is offered, and then the children listen to the work[8].

A positive aspect of concerts is that children are introduced to various musical instruments, and students from music schools and the teaching staff of the kindergarten perform. Children should not be tired by listening to music for a long time, as they lose interest in musical pieces, they listen inattentively, and, consequently, do not absorb musical material well. Listening as part of a regular music lesson can take 2-1 minutes, and a special lesson or concert, where children only listen to music, lasts 10-12 minutes in the middle group and 15-20 minutes in the senior and preparatory groups. Characteristics of the musical repertoire 1. Predominance of a range of bright, cheerful feelings and moods, since music affects the child physiologically. 2. Artistry of the musical repertoire. At preschool age, the prerequisites for the development of musical, aesthetic taste are laid, the first musical preferences appear. It is very important that preschoolers are brought up on musical samples that are generally recognized musical masterpieces, which does not exclude the use of modern, popular music that does not contradict this requirement. 3. Diversity of music. The musical repertoire should include both folklore and classical music, the best examples of

modern and specifically "children's" music. The presence of works of different styles and eras will enrich the auditory experience of preschoolers, expand their horizons, and make them receptive to various "musical languages"[10]. According to some studies, the ability to perceive various musical styles decreases with age, just as the ability to master verbal languages decreases (music and speech have a common intonational nature). 4. Accessibility of the work. Both according to the criteria of emotional accessibility, accessibility of musical language, and according to the criterion of time of perception of music (about 2 minutes of continuous sound); These requirements are met by the most famous works, which are increasingly used in the practice of work. Young children have a concrete way of thinking, they willingly listen to music associated with familiar, close images. Their attention is unstable and depends on the novelty and attractiveness of the objects of perception. [9].

They can listen attentively only to small musical pieces. Children of the middle group have an increasing interest in music, the volume of musical memory and attention increases somewhat. They acquire a certain skill of listening to music. Children should sit quietly while listening, and be able not only to listen to music, but also to recognize it. For example, children are asked to recognize a song by its melody sung without words, by its melody performed on an instrument, by its introduction. If children at first try to sing along with the teacher's voice, to move during the performance of instrumental music, he reminds them that this music should only be listened to. Listening to music in junior and middle groups is both an independent type of activity and a moment preceding children's singing and musical-rhythmic movements, since before children themselves begin to sing and play games and dances, they must receive a certain stock of musical impressions.

In the younger groups, in the process of listening to music, the teacher strives to: - accumulate musical impressions in children, evoke a joyful mood in them; - develop the ability to distinguish sounds by pitch, dynamics, timbre; listen to the piece to the end without being distracted, remember it; - develop the ability to feel the character of music, distinguish the simplest forms, tell what the song is about, recognize familiar pieces of music. In the process of listening to music in the middle group, the teacher should: - develop the ability to listen to music with interest, attentively, to the end, responding to its character and mood; - develop memory by recognizing a song, an instrumental piece by the melody played or sung without words; - cultivate interest and love for music, the desire to listen to it, accumulate musical impressions; - by means of music, promote the emergence of a feeling of love for the environment.

During lessons, while listening to music, children still receive very limited information aimed at explaining the works they listen to. It is even more important to demand precise, specific answers from children. Systematic exercises in listening to music develop children's stable auditory attention. This is what helps a child to perceive music more emotionally, more consciously, to feel the power of its impact. Following the rules of behavior in the process of listening to music and its simplest analysis gradually becomes a need and subsequently leads to the education of a cultured listener. In general, the music for children of primary and middle preschool age should be dominated by a range of bright, cheerful moods[1].

The subject matter of the pieces can be very diverse, but should relate to life phenomena that are close and understandable to children. In the practice of kindergartens, it is necessary to strive for a certain stability (constancy) of the repertoire, for a limited number of pieces. The fact that some songs, instrumental pieces will first be listened to by children, then, in another age group,

performed, and then become part of everyday life, will lead to a strong assimilation of the musical repertoire by children. Listening to music goes through three stages: 1. Initial acquaintance of children with a musical work. 2. Repeated listening, analysis of the work, drawing children's attention to the main means of musical expression. 3. Recognition of the work, clarification of individual means of expression. At each of these stages, certain teaching methods are used. At the first stage, the teacher must arouse interest in the work by expressively performing it. This is a mandatory requirement. The first performance of a piece of music should be especially heartfelt in order to leave a deep impression on the child's mind. At this stage, it is necessary to teach children to listen actively, to respond to the feelings expressed in the music, to perceive its general character. The teacher introduces children to the sphere of new musical impressions. His word on the music should be brief, figurative, and aimed at its main content. It is important to carefully think through the introductory word before the first listening to the music, as well as all subsequent explanations that will accompany the performance. In younger groups, during explanations, the teacher can use an artistic toy that helps to perceive the musical image[5].

Active musical perception should be judged by the children's statements, as well as by observing the child's facial expressions and facial expressions during listening, which indicate the children's interest or lack thereof. At the second stage - repeated listening - the teacher faces the task of activating the process of music perception. The teacher explains the composition of a piece of music, draws attention to the presence of an introduction, conclusion, and the main means of musical expression. In addition, toys and playful teaching methods can be used, and a picture can be shown that is thematically related to the content of the piece. At the third stage of listening to musical pieces, the child begins to recognize them, which indicates that ideas about music have been formed. As a result of frequent repetition of pieces, children remember and highlight the ones they like the most. They develop a selective attitude towards music. Children ask to perform their favorite pieces because they want to relive the feelings they evoke. It is desirable that musical pieces familiar to children are performed on different instruments - accordion, balalaika, button accordion, etc. This enriches children's musical perception and hearing, develops their memory and imagination. In older groups, work on listening to music continues and deepens. It acts as a section of the lesson, and as a methodical technique of work, and as an independent activity. The perception of children of this age becomes more conscious, controllable. The feelings evoked by music are more differentiated. Voluntary memory and attention are developed.

Children notice the similarity of musical pieces of the same genre, compare familiar pieces by their figurative content, the nature of the sound. Interest in a piece of music appears, and experiences and feelings become stable. Significant shifts are observed in children's thinking: a transition from visual-active to visual-figurative thinking occurs. Children's attention is already more stable, so they can listen to quite complex pieces. Children's speech is sufficiently developed, they are able to express their opinions about music, use various terms and definitions[6].

Their aesthetic experiences become deeper and richer (children react vividly and emotionally to the performance of works by the teacher, to the sound of music on a gramophone record). In the senior groups, in the process of listening to music, the teacher strives to: ♦ teach children to listen to music attentively, to express all their emotions after listening; ♦ cultivate an interest in vocal and instrumental music; instill an interest in listening to folk music, classical and modern, performed by soloists, choirs, instrumental ensembles of different compositions, and an orchestra; ♦ to teach children to remember pieces by their introduction and conclusion, by melody,

individual phrases, and parts; ♦ to develop the ability to distinguish the character of music, means of musical expression, and to express opinions about them; to distinguish between two- and three-part forms, song, dance, and marching genres; to develop the ability to compare pieces by similarity and contrast; ♦ to inspire the desire to listen to favorite pieces repeatedly.

Pieces intended for listening by older preschool children reflect a diverse range of feelings, moods, and numerous, but accessible to children's perception, events and phenomena of the surrounding reality. Vocal music still occupies the main place. Instrumental music becomes more diverse in its figurative content, combination of means of musical expression. The basis for the development of musical perception is still the expressive performance of works by a teacher or listening to music with the help of technical teaching aids, as well as the skillful use of words, toys, pictures, and applied art objects. Verbal techniques become more detailed, contributing to a deeper perception of musical works.

Children's life experience is widely used, new works are associated with already familiar ones. In the process of analyzing musical works, the requirements for children are gradually increased. During a conversation about the music they have listened to, the teacher encourages preschoolers to make independent statements. Conversations in which children learn, clarify and deepen the necessary information about music are conducted using comparisons, juxtapositions of musical works, with the gradual introduction of new concepts[11].

The teacher encourages children to associate the character of music with the content of the image, the mood expressed in it, and achieves more detailed statements, evaluative judgments about what they have heard. Sometimes before listening to program music, the teacher should compose a short figurative story. For example: *Maktabim, Chori Chambar, Gulbahor, "CHitti gul"* calling it. The active participation of children in the analysis of a piece of music is facilitated by the teacher's questions about its character, means of expression, form, content.

The questions should be clearly formulated, interest children, encourage them to make value judgments and their argumentation. In order to deepen the impressions of children, the teacher monitors the emotional coloring of his speech. If we talk about music in a dull, everyday language, then the work will not achieve the goal. Before performing a piece, it is very good to interest children with a poetic word - a fragment of a poem or song lyrics. For example, before listening to the Uzbek folk children's song "Oftob chiqdi" is recommended for publication for the first time.

He says that clowns are circus performers. At the next lesson, the teacher recalls with the children what new music they heard and clarifies its content with the words: "Look how cheerfully and merrily clowns jump and tumble! And who are clowns?" The teacher draws the children's attention to the nature of the music, and the children express their impressions of what they heard and name the piece. Of course, all explanations, clarifications, additions should be closely related to the direct perception of the music itself. In addition to performing the entire piece of music, you can play the most characteristic excerpts from it, but in no case at the first lesson. Sometimes he specially organizes observations of certain phenomena.

So, before letting them listen to the same piece "Fish", it is advisable to observe the movements of the fish in the aquarium in the nature corner. Observation is a very important method of educational work used by the teacher when listening to music. The process of introducing older children to musical works also includes three stages, where at each subsequent lesson the children learn new information and clarify what they have learned previously.

ЗУВ-ЗУВ БОРАҒАЙ

Ўзбек халқ ашуласи

Ўртача тезликда

Зув зув бо-ра-ғай тоғи-дан қо-ра-ғай у-зи ки-чи-га зам-ви ту-ғи-ғай

ОФТОБ ЧИКДИ

Ўзбек халқ ашуласи

Оф-тоб чик-ди о-лаи-га ю-гур-лаб бор-дим хо-лаи-га.

Хо-лаи кун-так теф-де-ди, те-риф мек-га бер-де-ди.

ЧИТТИ ГҮЛ

Ўзбек халқ ашуласи

чит-ти гул чит-ти гул э-та-ши-га гул бо-сай.

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